

PHRASEOLOGISMS AS MIRROR OF CULTURE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6550543>

Mukhamedova M.A.

year Master's student of

The National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Nazirova Sh.O.

Faculty of Foreign philology

Scientific supervisor: PhD

Annotation: *There are phraseologisms specific to each nation as well as cultures specific to each nation. It is clear that phraseologisms express the values of the nation to which they belong. Looking at these cultural expressions, we can easily have more or less idea about those folks. Therefore, phraseological units have an important place in our life. A lot of scientists have researched on this sphere and it is still one of the interesting themes for linguists nowadays. The present article is devoted to investigation of correlation of culture and phraseologisms. The following methods of the research were used: descriptive method, comparative and cross-cultural analysis.*

Key words: *phraseologism, culture, idioms, phraseological units, vocabulary, skill.*

As in every language, there are phraseologisms or idioms in every culture. Culture is characteristic of a nation. Culture represents traditions and customs specific to that nation. In a sense, phraseological units are indicative of cultural partnership. Individuals' effective use of language skills depends on vocabulary. It is not only the words that make up this, the phraseological units play an active role in this affirmation. Since language is an effective communication tool, it helps individuals to integrate culturally. In this sense phraseologisms greatly influence and improve the cultural dimension of language. Phraseological units give clues to the culture of a country. The expression of each country is unique [8].

The most valuable sources of information about the culture, national character, psychological peculiarities and mentality of the nation one can find in phraseological units. Phraseological units very often reflect the peculiarities of the culture of the language they belong to; moreover they reflect history of that nation, their attitude towards world, stereotypes they believe in, etc. Furthermore, phraseological units usually are formed from national sayings, prejudices, and cultural traditions, and represent quite a large part of linguistics. Phraseological units are common to all languages of the world but have their unique form of expression. Their national -cultural specifics is shown in translation process.

Phraseological units are considered as rich sources of social-historical information [7]. That's why their formation closely connected with extra-linguistic factors. Such units are able to reflect nature of any place, economic-social conditions and culture of a definite nation, history, way of living, folk art, literature, science, traditions, customs which are

passed from generation to generation. It preserves the ideas of people on myths, customs, ceremonies, rituals, habits, morals, behavior etc. There are some scholars which analyzed the culture and phraseologisms relationship and they gave their conclusion about this process. According to the classification compiled by A. F. Artyomova and O. A. Leonovich, there are 4 semantic groups of phraseological units (PhUs):

1) PhUs with the component "proper name" of biblical origin, for example: Job's comforter – a person who tries to comfort people but occasionally makes their misfortune even harder;

2) PhUs with the component "proper name" of mythological origin, for example: a labor of Sisyphus – hard and fruitless labor;

3) PhUs with the component "proper name" associated with the geography, history, literature and life of the English, such as: doctor Fell – a person who causes antipathy to himself;

4) phraseological units with the component "proper name" of American origin, for instance: Peck's Bad Boy – a malicious simpleton [1].

According to this classification we can see that each group of phraseological units is connected to people's cultural life. They cannot be apart from them. Another linguist B.A. Larin noted that phraseological units always indirectly reflect people's views, social order and ideology of the epoch [2]. And according to F.I. Buslaev, phraseological units are peculiar microcosms. They comprise «both the moral law, and the common sense, expressed in a short saying, which were entrusted to the descendants by their ancestors». A.V. Kunin follows I.S. Narsky and considers invariant of information as «something which is constantly preserved in the process of transformation of information». V.N. Teliya claims that the phraseological fund of the language is «a mirror in which the lingual and cultural community identifies its national consciousness». Phraseological units impose a special vision of the world, situation to native speakers [8]. For example, in English a baker's dozen (according to the ancient custom, bread tradesmen received thirteen loaves instead of twelve from bakers, and the thirteenth loaf was taken into an income of tradesmen); good wine needs no bush (according to the ancient custom, innkeepers hung out ivy branches meaning that there was wine on sale) [4]. One should know that imaginative thinking of people is often special, it is reflected in a phraseological units and sometimes creates opportunity for comparisons and metaphorical representations for the people of different cultures and makes the phraseological unit the national phenomenon of each culture [2]. An English idiom has kissed the blarney stone (the Blarney Stone) is the nationally-marked phraseological unit. It means to be the flatterer. This saying is based on an ancient legend, according to which the one, who kisses the stone, located in the Irish Blarney, gains the ability to flatter [5].

In conclusion, phraseological units and idioms are one of the most significant parts of the national culture, great richness of the generations. Idioms occur in languages on the base of imaginative representation of our reality, which reflects empirical and spiritual experience of the linguistic community. The system of images in the phraseology of language is connected with material, social and cultural aspects of the given linguistic community, we should admit that it also testifies about its cultural, national experience

and traditions. Summarizing all that mentioned above, we can say that phraseological units show national culture specifics and mostly have equivalents in other languages.

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